

Wave-like global economic ripple response to Hurricane Sandy

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Abstract

Tropical cyclones range among the costliest disasters on Earth. Their economic repercussions along the supply and trade network also affect remote economies that are not directly affected. We here simulate possible global repercussions on consumption for the example case of Hurricane Sandy in the US (2012) using the shock-propagation model *Acclimate*. The modeled shock yields a global three-phase ripple: an initial production demand reduction and associated consumption price decrease, followed by a supply shortage with increasing prices, and finally a recovery phase. Regions with strong trade relations to the US experience strong magnitudes of the ripple. A dominating demand reduction or supply shortage leads to overall consumption gains or losses of a region, respectively. While finding these repercussions in historic data is challenging due to strong volatility of economic interactions, numerical models like ours can help to identify them by approaching the problem from an exploratory angle, isolating the effect of interest. For this, our model simulates the economic interactions of over 7,000 regional economic sectors, interlinked through about 1.8 million trade relations. Under global warming, the wave-like structures of the economic response to major hurricanes like the one simulated here are likely to intensify and potentially overlap with other weather extremes.

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Introduction

Globally, tropical cyclones range among the costliest and deadliest natural disasters. While they constitute only 16.5% of all recorded billion-dollar events in the United States between 1980 and 2018, they are responsible for more than half of the costs resulting from all extreme weather events combined^{1;2}. Their frequency is expected to decrease or to remain static under global warming but most projections anticipate an increase in intensity of the most extreme tropical cyclones³, especially in the Atlantic basin⁴ (where tropical cyclones are called hurricanes). In consequence, economic losses in hurricane-prone regions are expected to increase in the future due to climate change^{5;6;7;8} through higher storm intensity⁹ and sea level rise¹⁰ but also due to changes in the economic values at risk^{11;12}. Local economies can be affected through destroyed capital stock (stock losses or damages) or through lost production output (flow losses). Since we do not consider damages in this work, we here generally imply lost production in the notion of loss. In particular, we refer to losses in a region that is directly affected by a hurricane as direct losses. However, losses can spread through the supply network, which is then referred to as higher-order losses^{13;14;15}. We here refer to the latter as indirect losses. These may represent a substantial or even dominant share of total economic disaster losses^{16;17;18}. Indirect losses can result from supply shortages due to direct losses that propagate downstream along supply chains. Direct losses and an associated production decrease may also lead to reduced demand (production demand, generally in contrast to final demand for household consumption) which propagates upstream in the supply network. These downstream and upstream effects are also called forward and backward propagation¹⁹ or ripple effects²⁰. Here, we investigate the possible ripple response to Hurricane Sandy (2012) and its effect on global consumption expenditure.

There is good consensus in the literature that extreme weather events have adverse effects on household consumption²¹, which is commonly used in economic models as a measure for societal welfare²² and is therefore often regarded in disaster impact analyses. In this study, we refer to the latter as final consumption or simply consumption where we also include government spending. In a globalised world, local disasters can have global economic repercussions²³, one prime example being the COVID-19 pandemic²⁴ with huge estimated indirect consumption losses worldwide²⁵. However, most studies^{26;27;28;29} on the impacts of historic extreme weather events focus on the local economic impacts of the disaster and therefore miss the global dimension²³.

With this work, we choose a different scope of analysis and investigate a single historic hurricane's possible impact on consumption on a global scale. We simulate the potential global indirect impacts on consumption that a major hurricane in the United States can have globally, using an agent-based network model. We choose a modeling approach because this allows us to investigate aspects of higher-order effects of a single event that

cannot be found in historic data. While local effects of hurricanes are — in large parts — well-studied^{30;31;32}, higher-order effects and the way they propagate in the trade network are still poorly understood. Lenzen et al. (2019)¹⁴ conducted a study on the higher-order indirect effects of a single hurricane in Australia but focus on national spillover effects. Other studies^{7;33;34} give a global perspective but cannot link effects to single historic events or do not consider indirect losses. We here propose one means to study loss propagation and global effects on consumption after a single historic major hurricane. As a case study, we choose Hurricane Sandy which made landfall in the US in 2012.

Sandy severely hit the US and in particular the states of New York (NY) and New Jersey (NJ) in 2012. It was the fourth-costliest hurricane in history and caused an estimated total damage of \$65bn³⁵ (in 2012 US Dollar), predominantly by driving a storm surge into the coastlines of NY and NJ³⁶. Given the magnitude of this local economic shock and the importance of the economically strong regions of NY and NJ in the global trade network, Hurricane Sandy most likely also entailed indirect effect in regions not directly affected. To understand how these repercussions may have spread in the global supply and trade network, we here simulate global consumption expenditure across the global economy in the direct aftermath of the strong economic shock in NY and NJ after Sandy.

We thereby add to the discussion on the welfare impacts of extreme weather events in two major points. First, by taking a modeling approach, we can go beyond a local case study and simulate consumption impacts globally as a result of production shortages and price effects propagating in the global supply network. This allows us to investigate effects that are otherwise hidden in coarse and noisy data. We find that although directly affected regions show the strongest effects, we observe an overall impact on consumption on the global level. Regions with strong trade relations to the US are affected most. Second, our approach allows us to analyse the underlying propagation effects inside our model that lead to the observed global consumption anomalies. The propagation follows a three-phase ripple of prices. An initial upstream effect results in price decreases and associated consumption increases. The following downstream effect leads to price increases and reduced consumption, followed by a normalization phase.

Method overview

Our simulations are carried out using the dynamic agent-based model *Acclimate*³⁷ which models loss-propagation on the global supply network, assuming a demand-driven economy. In this model, economic sectors (in case of the United States and China on a state and province level respectively, otherwise on a national level) are modeled as agents that are interlinked through trade flows, with each agent maximizing its own profit. The economy of each region is divided into 27 sectors, including the final consumer. With a total of 268 modeled regions, this results in over 7,000 agents. By applying an external

shock in the form of a reduction in the production capacity of one or more agents, the initial baseline state of equilibrium can be disturbed. We model this production shock to represent the direct losses due to Hurricane Sandy in the affected areas of New York and New Jersey. We use a disaggregated³⁸ version of the EORA MRIO dataset for the year 2012³⁹ as economic baseline. *Acclimate* then simulates anomalies around this baseline state that result from the production capacity reduction by profit-maximization of each individual agent on a daily time scale. Prices in the model are endogenous variables which account for local scarcities and transport costs. They always reflect price changes relative to baseline prices and do not represent absolute prices of traded goods (which are unknown since they are not contained in the EORA dataset).

The conceptual approach of this study is summarised in [Fig. 1](#). We model the direct economic impact from Hurricane Sandy for NY and NJ only (orange and blue, respectively), although another ten states and the District of Columbia (DC) were also affected (hatched areas). However, NY and NJ were most affected, receiving more than 96% of Congress' Disaster Relief Appropriations Act funds from January 2013 (\$50.5bn in total)⁴⁰. And according to estimates of the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration¹, the damage share for all other areas is less than 5% of the total damage. We derive production shocks for NY and NJ ([Supplementary Fig. 1](#), [Supplementary Tbl. 1](#)) based on estimated business interruption (BI) due to the disaster. In this, we assume all sectors to be affected in the same way. While this is generally a strong assumption, we find it reasonable for the short time in the immediate aftermath of the hurricane. We then analyse the resulting global levels of final consumption and related prices as well as production levels, production prices, and demands communicated in the network to assess the higher-order repercussions of Hurricane Sandy. These result from the inter-linkages of NY and NJ within the global trade network (exemplary trade flows in [Fig. 1](#)). For a detailed description of the approach, see [Appendix A: Methods](#).

Three-phase consumption ripple

We compute the relative consumption change in the first 100 days after the disaster for all regions globally ([Fig. 2](#), [Supplementary Tbl. 2](#)). A region's consumption change is computed as the ratio between the absolute aggregated difference from baseline consumption and the consumption that these regions would exhibit in the unperturbed baseline scenario during this time (eq. (5) in [Appendix A: Methods](#)).

A normalisation of consumption and consumption prices in the United States of America occurs about 100 days after the event ([Fig. 3](#)). On a national level, the US show the strongest consumption decrease of all regions within our study. However, on a US state level we find both consumption increases as well as losses ([Fig. 2b](#)) in our simulations. Within the US, there is a strong correlation between the gross regional production (GRP)

Figure 1: Conceptual design of the study. Hurricane Sandy (track shown as dotted line) resulted in physical damages in multiple US states. New York (orange) and New Jersey (blue) received the largest damages. Dark gray shaded states were affected in a comparatively minor way (see main text) and production shocks in these states therefore are not considered. We derive a disaster-driven reduction of production capacity for NY and NJ based on the GRP of counties with reported high water marks (hatched areas) and estimated recovery duration from business interruptions. We simulate the resulting impacts on global consumption through loss propagation in the global trade network. As an example, we here show import and export volumes of New York and New Jersey with Europe, China, Canada, and Mexico, aggregated over all sectors. Trade flows are directed from the sharp end to the large end of a wedge. The width of the large end shows the trade flow magnitude. Note that in the actual model, there are potentially trade flows between any two of the over 7,000 economic agents, consisting of 27 sectors in 268 simulated regions. All region shape files retrieved from GADM⁴¹, storm track from IBTrACS⁴².

Figure 2: Consumption changes in the direct aftermath of Hurricane Sandy. Changes relative to baseline values during the first 100 days after the disaster (eq. (5)) are shown **a** globally and **b** for the US only. Red and purple shading indicate a consumption decrease compared to baseline consumption, blue and yellow shading indicate a consumption increase. Grey areas are excluded from the calculation due to low data quality.

of a state and its consumption change. Economically strong states like California, Texas, or Florida exhibit strong consumption decreases whereas consumption increases in states with a lower GRP like Vermont, Wyoming, or Montana.

Both increases and reductions in consumption are a result of consumption price changes. The consumption level depends directly on the consumption price with sector and region specific consumption price elasticities (see [Appendix A: Methods, Supplementary Tbl. 2, Supplementary Tbl. 3, Supplementary Tbl. 4](#)). The latter reflect the sensitivity of consumption (quantity) to price changes. Of course, post-disaster price elasticities might deviate from those during normal times. However, this is difficult to estimate and only relevant for the final consumption in the directly affected states NY and NJ. Consumption in all other regions can be assumed to follow normal elasticities. Previous sensitivity analysis⁴³ on model-internal price elasticities showed that this parameter choice has no significant impact on results derived via *Acclimate*.

In all regions, we observe an initial consumption price drop directly after the disaster, resulting in a consumption level above baseline. This initial price drop results from a reduction in the (production) demand of the directly affected states of NY and NJ and its quick upstream propagation along the global supply chains. Therefore, reducing demand instantaneously results in a situation of surplus supply, which causes prices to decline and consumption to rise. However, direct production losses in NY and NJ simultaneously propagate downstream through the global supply network and result in scarcity situations also in other regions that are not directly affected. As a result, shortly after the initial small consumption increase, consumption prices rise again with prices in US states reaching values above baseline level only few days after the hurricane and a maximum peak at over +1.3% about 30 days after the disaster. In case of the United States, the initial price drop associated with increased consumption is therefore quickly reversed by a scarcity driven price inflation resulting in a reduction in consumption. While the

Figure 3: Changes of consumption and consumption prices relative to baseline values. All values are in percent compared to baseline levels (dashed lines). **left column** Relative consumption price change. **right column** Relative consumption change. **upper panels** Results for the directly affected US states NY and NJ and all remaining US states and DC (in grey shades). **middle panels** Results for Mexico and Canada. **lower panels** Results for Europe, Germany and China.

upstream effect happens without time delay, the downstream propagation of scarcities is initially buffered by the agents' inventories but also by transport chains through which goods are delivered. Therefore, in contrast to demand shortages propagating upstream, the downstream propagation of scarcities only shows effects with some lag time. The persisting shortage of supply leads to price inflation of intermediate goods that are passed on to the final consumers. As a consequence, the latter have to decrease their consumption. A normalisation of US prices and consumption occurs about 100 days after the event. While the US are most impacted by the event, changes from the baseline economic state due to the hurricane event occur globally. A similar development with an initial small consumption increase followed by a stronger counter effect of decreasing consumption can be observed — yet with smaller magnitude — in Mexico and Canada, which have strong trade relations with the United States.

Generally, consumption shows a three-phase wave pattern of an initial price drop due to upstream effects, followed by a price increase attributable to downstream effects and finally a normalisation phase where prices develop back towards baseline values. Depending on how strong the upstream and downstream effects are with regards to a particular region, average prices range above or below baseline. For example, the upstream effect

for Canada and Mexico is small compared to the downstream effect, leading to higher average prices. In Europe and its strongest economy Germany as well as China, the initial price drop due to the fast upstream effect is large enough to permanently keep prices below baseline (Fig. 3e).

Regions' trade with the US

In the simulated disaster aftermath, the magnitude of the effect on a region's consumption depends on the trade relations of that region with the US (i.e., the sum of all imports and exports, Fig. 4a), following a power law relationship. Both high import and export trade flows result in a strong consumption changes (Supplementary Fig. 2). Linear regression in the log-log space indicates an exponent that is below 1, i.e. the absolute consumption difference increases less than linearly with growing trade volume with the US. Regions with strong trade relations experience a stronger price effect. However, due to the prescribed negative price elasticities, this price effect affects consumption less than linearly.

Whether or not a region experiences total gains or losses in consumption depends on the country-specific shape of the three-phase ripple, i.e. whether the upstream or downstream effects is dominant. To show this, we analyse additional simulations with longer recovery times (80, 100, 120 days, Fig. 4), which mainly intensifies the slower propagating downstream effect (Supplementary Fig. 3). Initially, most regions (with the exception of Mexico, Canada and the Philippines) show consumption gains. With longer duration, the latter decrease and consumption losses increase. With a recovery time extension of 20 days (Fig. 4b), additional regions transitions from gains to losses (e.g. Australia, Venezuela, Ireland, Singapore, Hong Kong). The initially small consumption loss increases with further recovery time extension (panels c, d). Likewise, regions like Canada, Mexico and the Philippines that show losses already with the original recovery time further increase their losses. In the case of Mexico and Canada, this can supposedly be explained by the geographic and economic proximity of the regions to the US, resulting in a faster downstream propagation to these countries. This suggests that each region has an individual threshold where the direct impact in NY and NJ becomes too strong and a dominating downstream effect results in overall consumption losses. This threshold is already crossed for the Philippines as well as Mexico and Canada with the original recovery time of 60 days.

Generally, the consumption reaction of all regions to the shock duration in NY and NJ appears to follow an inverted U-shape. Without a shock, all regions consume at their baseline level. Short shocks result in consumption gains that increase with the shock duration at first. At some point — depending on the trade relations with the US — consumption gains decrease and eventually transition into losses. Regions with a large trade volume tend to transition sooner than those with smaller trade to the US.

Price dynamics

So far we analysed the consumption price and resulting consumption levels on a regional level and found a three-phased ripple that can result in both overall gains and losses of consumption. In the following, we investigate the underlying price dynamics that lead this ripple which originates in the directly affected regions NY and NJ. For this, we look at changes of production prices and levels of incoming demand as well as changes of the capacity utilization in NY and NJ as well as the rest of the US. We use the economic notion of capacity utilization⁴⁴ that is defined as the ratio of actual output to the output that would minimise production costs. This measure quantifies if and by how much a region is in a state of overproduction, relative to the actual production capacity. For the directly affected regions, we need to first adjust production capacity for the applied production shock. We also calculate the similarly adjusted demand exceedance which indicates if fulfilling the entire incoming demand at a given time step would drive the agent into overproduction, i.e. by how much current incoming demand exceeds the production capacity (for both adjusted capacity utilization and demand exceedance see [Appendix A: Methods](#)). Time series for production prices, demand exceedance and capacity utilization in our simulations are shown in [Fig. 5](#) for the directly affected US states NJ and NY as well as an aggregate over all other US states and DC. We refer to the latter in the following as USA-OTH.

In the *Acclimate* model, production prices and ultimately consumption prices are driven by the demand that agents receive. In the immediate aftermath of the disaster, NY and NJ cannot satisfy their incoming demand due to the applied external reduction of production capacity. This is reflected by a high demand exceedance. As a result, the directly affected states switch to overproduction directly after the disaster, similarly indicated by an increased capacity utilization. At the same time, NY and NJ reduce their demand towards other regions. Due to the resulting initial upstream propagation, the remainder of the US does not fully use the available production capacity and production prices decrease at first (note that the apparent contradiction for the pooled region USA-OTH of positive demand exceedance and simultaneous low capacity utilization during the first days after the disaster is simply a result of the aggregation that we perform over the US regions and their individual sectors, see [Appendix A: Methods](#)). However, the longer the disruption prevails, the more of the lost production in NY and NJ propagates downstream in the economic network, resulting in scarcity of goods. This scarcity is compensated by other US states and also the latter eventually switch to overproduction. Yet, overproduction comes at the cost of production prices increasing super-linearly with the production level and average prices rise above baseline levels during this upstream phase. In the situation of scarcity in the disaster aftermath, agents in the network are willing to pay these higher-than-usual prices and producing agents keep their increased production level.

We observe this behaviour of rising production prices until about 45 days after the disaster, when production prices rapidly drop again. This drop marks the beginning of the normalization phase. Note that it coincides with a change of the capacity utilization change from positive to negative values, causing agents to switch from an overproduction state to a normal production regime. The sudden price drop results from the fact that now production prices no longer depend super-linearly on the produced quantity. Two factors lead to the end of the overproduction regime: (i) many purchasing firms decide simultaneously to reduce their demand due to the high level of prices, and (ii) the reduction of production capacity in the directly affected states is released enough so that the new, reduced incoming demand can be satisfied without overproduction.

As can be seen in Fig. 5, the demand exceedance for NY and NJ decreases exponentially after the disaster, which is simply due to the defined exponential economic recovery. About 45 days after the event, when we observe the production price drop, the production capacity reduction has released enough for smaller demand variations to cause the demand exceedance to drop below 0. Such variations are a result of the complex dynamics of the model. Since each agent may redistribute its demand in each time step and will do so in order to maximise its profit, the incoming demand (and hence, the demand exceedance) is subject to some fluctuation. The price tension that previously built up in the network releases and prices drop back towards baseline levels.

A schematic time evolution for the analysed quantities of a directly affected agent is shown in Fig. 6 (panels a–d) with coincident events and phases in the aftermath of the hurricane (panel d). While we expect the general behaviour of directly affected agents to may be similar for other natural disasters that show an exponential business interruption recovery, time scales and magnitudes may well be different and are therefore omitted in the figure.

Discussion

In this study, we modeled the impact that a severe disaster like Hurricane Sandy (2012) can have on global consumption, resulting from economic forward and backward loss propagation in the global supply network. We find a three-phase economic ripple in the supply chain network. This ripple is characterized by an initial upstream effect and resulting consumption increase, followed by an opposing and slower downstream effect and associated reduced consumption. The last phase is a price normalization.

The magnitude of consumption effects on a region depends on its trade volume with the US. Whether a region experiences overall gains or losses depends on which of the upstream or downstream effect during the ripple is dominating. In our simulations, most regions experience slight consumption gains. With longer duration of the direct impact, these regions show a tendency of decreasing consumption gains and eventually a transition

to consumption losses. Many regions experience these losses already with an additional recovery time of only 20 days. This is important for two reasons. First, direct losses of hurricanes must be expected to increase in the future due to climate change^{45;8}, resulting in potentially longer recovery durations. Second, the recovery from business interruption was particularly quick after Hurricane Sandy and it can take much longer for other economies subjected to different natural disasters to recover. In the case of Hurricane Katrina in 2005, the economic activity recovered to pre-disaster levels only about one year later⁴⁶.

Of course, results from socioeconomic models like the one used in this study are subject to uncertainties due to the necessary assumptions on which the model builds. In particular, these uncertainties concern the absolute magnitudes of the reported results which may appear small at first sight. We emphasize that these values result from only one local, isolated extreme weather event and are therefore still considerable. Previous research⁴⁷ has also shown that economic ripples from disasters can amplify each other. More importantly however, we stress the *qualitative* nature and importance of our findings regarding the economic ripple. Our finding of a three-phase ripple and related consumption changes is qualitatively robust against variations of the local production disruption (Supplementary Fig. 3, Supplementary Fig. 4, Supplementary Fig. 5).

While we focused on the specific regions of New York and New Jersey in the United States for this study, similar ripple waves can be expected for major shocks in other regions of the world. Besides hurricanes, we also expect other categories of extreme weather events to have similar economic impacts on consumption. Consecutive and compound events (e.g. the 2020 flood in China and the concurrent heat wave in Europe as recent examples) will likely further increase the magnitudes of the observed indirect effects. Since all these extremes are projected to intensify — at least on a local level — under global warming⁴⁸, we believe that modeling approaches like the one we conducted here can contribute valuable insights for necessary mitigation by allowing to simulate and better understand higher-order effects that otherwise cannot be studied.

Code availability

The implementation of the *Acclimate* model is available as open source on <https://github.com/acclimate/acclimate> with identifier [10.5281/zenodo.853345](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.853345). The code for data processing and analysis scripts is available from the corresponding author upon request.

Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon request. GADM region shape files can be found at <http://www.gadm.org>. Storm track retrieved from IBTrACS database at <http://ibtracs.unca.edu/>.

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Author contributions

R.M., S.W., and C.O. designed the method. S.W. and C.O. developed the Acclimate model. K.K. provided the price elasticities. R.M. conducted the analysis. R.M., S.W., C.O., and A.L. analysed and interpreted the results. R.M., S.W., C.O., K.K., L.Q., and A.L. discussed the results and wrote the manuscript.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Figure 4: Consumption change over total trade volume with the US with varied recovery times. Consumption changes are cumulated for the first 100 days after the hurricane. US trade volume is the sum of a region’s total exports and imports with the United States. Size of the scatters indicates the consumption change relative to what regions would consume under baseline conditions during this time. Green and red colors indicate consumption gains and losses, respectively. The dashed line is the linear fit in the log-log space. Recovery time is set to **a** 60 (default recovery), **b** 80, **c** 100 and **d** 120 days.

Figure 5: Production price, demand exceedance and capacity utilization for the United States. Directly affected states NJ and NY are shown individually, remaining 48 states and DC are aggregated as USA-OTH. Dashed lines represent baseline values. **a** Changes of the production price from baseline values. **b** Demand exceedance relative to baseline values. **c** Relative change in capacity utilization from baseline values.

Figure 6: Schematic time evolution of a directly affected agent. Dashed lines represent baseline values. Explicit values and durations are not given because magnitudes and time scales differ between disasters. **a** Production capacity reduction factor with initial production shock λ_0 . **b** Relative production price change. Grey shaded area denotes the price pressure development time until the price drop. **c** Demand exceedance. Grey shaded area denotes the time during which the economic shock has not decayed enough for demand variations to end the overproduction regime. Noise is due to demand fluctuation from the profit maximization and associated demand shifts of all agents. When the production capacity has recovered enough, this noise can be strong enough to make an agent switch from an overproduction to a normal production regime (production regime change). **d** Relative change in capacity utilization. Light grey area denotes the time during which the agent does not fulfill the incoming demand while in a state of overproduction. The dark grey shaded area is the time during which the entire demand can be satisfied with overproduction. **e** Timeline with the initial disaster impact, the consumption price peak and upstream, downstream and normalisation phases.

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Appendices for:

Wave-like global economic ripple response to Hurricane Sandy

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Appendix A: Methods

Business interruption recovery

We assume the business interruption (BI) to be very strong but short, representing the short-term disruptions after the storm that can be quickly recovered from to an extent that most business processes are again functional, e.g. interruptions due to power outages, flooding, transportation disruption, and disturbance in communication. We set the initial intensity of this BI for NY and NJ to the GDP share of the respective state that is physically exposed to the hurricane. As damage from Sandy was primarily due to precipitation and flooding, we focus on this physical factor. For that, we calculate GDP exposure on a county level. We consider those counties as exposed for which the U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) reported at least one high water mark¹.

We then assume exponential recovery from the BI as is commonly done with disaster recovery^{2,3}, assuming a rather efficient recovery of the local economy⁴ which we esteem realistic for the economically strong regions of NY and NJ. The intuitive reason for using exponential recovery in this case is that most effective measures of recovery can be believed to take place first. Subsequent measures may be less effective in comparison to their effort, resulting in an exponential path of recovery. As an example, power supply was restored exponentially after Hurricane Sandy⁵. We can also observe exponential recovery after Hurricane Katrina as measured by the Louisiana Coincident Economic Activity Index⁶ (the index is based on non-farm payroll employment, the unemployment rate, average hours worked in manufacturing, and wages and salaries). However, this is a long-term recovery over about one year and therefore presumably cannot be explained by BI alone but potentially also reflects losses due to reconstruction efforts and capital stock losses. To estimate a time scale for the exponential decay of the BI shock, we similarly use unemployment as a proxy. The Federal Reserve Bank of New York found unemployment claims in NY and NJ to rise due to Sandy with the number of initial claims showing a roughly exponential decay (see Fig. 1 in Abel et al. (2013)⁷) after an initial peak. According to this report, “both states saw employment rebound to above October (pre-Sandy) levels by the end of the year” 2012. We therefore fit our BI recovery to end after 60 days. (see [Appendix A: Methods](#) for details). This time scale is also in accordance with a Downtown

Alliance report⁸ which finds that over 95% of Manhattan office space was available again after Sandy by the end of the year 2012.

Note that our notion of recovery does not include any concept of growth, i.e. we consider recovery as completed once output quantities equal those before the disaster. Generally, disasters can have long-term or even permanent effects⁹ and it has been shown that tropical cyclones have long-term impacts on economic growth¹⁰ with effects lasting as long as 20 years¹¹. Unlike for fluvial floods, countries with higher development are not well prepared against the impact of tropical cyclones and their associated long-term growth losses¹². Since we focus here on the short-term impacts, we do not model growth and assume a constant baseline economy, resulting in much shorter recovery times.

We assume an initial production capacity reduction factor λ_0 in the direct aftermath of the disaster as the share of state GDP that is exposed to the disaster. We use reported high water marks associated with the disaster to determine how severely individual states are affected. We retrieve high water marks from the USGS Flood Event Viewer¹. We consider each county within a state as affected by the disaster if it has at least one reported high water mark. We then calculate the relative GDP exposure, i.e. the initial production capacity reduction λ_0 , of the entire state from

$$\lambda_0 = \frac{\sum_{c \in C} GDP_c}{GDP_s} \quad (1)$$

where GDP_c is the GDP of an affected county from the set of all affected counties C and GDP_s is the overall state's GDP.

While this approach to determine the initial production capacity reduction of a directly affected state is a rather simple one, we believe that it is still sufficiently good to achieve a realistic scenario of direct economic losses. Given that this initial reduction of production capacity level only prevails for a very short time and then is gradually relieved by the exponential recovery curve, we esteem variations in this value as less crucial for the outcome of the simulations than the direct economic loss which determines how long the production capacity reduction persists. For NY and NJ, we obtain initial production shock of $\sim 80.2\%$ and $\sim 69.3\%$, respectively. This matches observations rather well. According to the Empire State Manufacturing Survey¹³ by the Federal Reserve Bank of New York, more than 90% of all businesses in the New York City area were shut down for at least one day due to Hurricane Sandy. For example, the New York stock exchange was shut down for two days after the hurricane¹. The New York-Newark-Jersey City Metropolitan Statistical Area (NYMSA) accounts for a 2012 GDP of about \$1.4bn and counts mostly to the GDP of New York and New Jersey (and a negligible fraction for Pennsylvania with only one county). NY and NJ have a combined 2012 GDP of about \$1.8bn. Using GDP as a proxy for economic activity, we thus may assume that a 90% one-day shut down in the

¹<https://www.theguardian.com/world/2012/oct/31/new-york-stock-exchange-opens-sandy>

NYMSA is equivalent to a 68.4% one-day shutdown for both states combined. However, this number does not include businesses that were only partly disrupted and must hence be considered a lower bound for economic disruption. Our estimates for New York and New Jersey with 80.2% and 69.3% therefore seem reasonable for the day immediately following the hurricane.

After the disaster, we assume exponential recovery of the economy back to 100% from the initial production shock given by eq. (1). Reduction in productive capacity is then given by

$$f(t) := 1 - \lambda_0 e^{-t/\tau} \quad (2)$$

with initial shock λ_0 and characteristic time scale τ . We assume that full recovery is given at time t_r once the shock has decayed to 0.1% or less, i.e. $f_r = f(t_r) \geq 0.999$. With a prescribed recovery time t_r , we thus can derive τ :

$$\begin{aligned} f(t_r) = f_r &= 1 - \lambda_0 e^{-t_r/\tau} \\ \Rightarrow \tau &= -\frac{t_r}{\ln\left(\frac{1-f_r}{\lambda_0}\right)} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The fully parametrised curve for the reduction of production capacity is then given by

$$f_{\lambda_0, f_r}(t) := \begin{cases} 1 - \lambda_0 e^{-t/\tau_{\lambda_0, f_r, t_r}} & \text{for } t \leq t_r \\ 1 & \text{for } t > t_r. \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

For the US states NY and NJ with recovery time $t_r = 60$, this yields the production capacity reduction curves shown in [Supplementary Fig. 1](#). The initial production capacity reduction values λ_0 are listed in [Supplementary Tbl. 1](#).

Indirect and consumption losses

To simulate indirect and consumption losses, we use the dynamic agent-based model *Acclimate*¹⁴. This model has been presented in different versions previously^{15;16;14} and was used in studies regarding the higher-order economic losses from extreme weather events^{17;18;19}. We here use the latest model presented in Otto et al. (2017)¹⁴. In this model, regional economic sectors are represented by individual agents that are interconnected through trade flows. The resolution of these regions is on a state-level in case of the United States, province-level in case of China and national level for all other regions of the world, resulting in a total of 268 individual regions. The economy is split into 27 sectors, including the final consumer as one sector without production output. All sectors of a region that is directly affected by the hurricane are subjected to the same production reduction curves as per eq. (4). Trade flows between the resulting total of 7,263 agents are taken

from a disaggregated²⁰ version of the EORA multi-regional input-output dataset²¹. This data set contains annual monetary flows between the agents from the year 2012. We break this down to a monetary daily baseline flow by distributing equally over 365 days which we refer to as baseline equilibrium flow. This is the state around which *Acclimate* simulates deviations resulting from an externally enforced reduction of production capacity. This production shock results in perturbations of demand, supply and prices within the model, globally. The dynamics is a result from the profit maximisation that each individual agent performs by optimising production levels, demand distribution to suppliers and upstream demand to other agents. In this, increased demand from other agents can be addressed by activation of idle production capacities, resulting in elevated production prices. A comprehensive description of the model can be found in the original publication by Otto et al. (2017)¹⁴.

For the present study, we look into the output variables of production, final consumption, and communicated demands along the supply chains as well as associated prices. Using the 2012 EORA dataset, the baseline flows must be considered influenced by the economic shock of Hurricane Sandy. However, this influence is small compared to the total volume of trade flows such that the introduced bias is negligible. For example, the impact of Hurricane Sandy on GDP in remote regions cannot be found in historic data.

While included in the simulations, for all calculations and analyses in this study, we exclude the EORA regions of Belarus, Moldova, Sudan, and South Sudan since the data quality for these regions is not reliable, especially with regards to final consumption.

Aggregate relative consumption changes $\Delta \bar{C}_r$ in each simulated region r for the direct aftermath of the hurricane are calculated from the simulated consumption levels as follows:

$$\Delta \bar{C}_r = -1 + \frac{1}{(T - t_0) c_r^*} \sum_{t=t_0}^T c_r^{(t)} \quad (5)$$

where $c_r^{(t)}$ is the final consumption in region r at time step t , c_r^* is the baseline consumption and $(T - t_0)$ is the time of aggregation after the disaster.

Consumption prices

Consumers in the model, like other agents, purchase at a price which they propose to producers together with their demand request. This reservation price is oriented towards offer prices that producers advertise to their trade partners. The entirety of reservation prices and the production quantity resulting from a producer's optimization process determine the final production price. The latter in turn influences the offer price that producers advertise. Therefore, in case of rising production prices, consumers also need to pay higher prices to ensure that their demand will be fulfilled. Production prices and consumer purchasing prices are therefore related. However, the measured consumption price is

buffered by storage inventories that fill up and thus smooth production prices. Hence, the consumption price is an average of the goods' prices currently in storage and therefore averages production prices over a certain amount of time.

Capacity utilisation and demand exceedance

Capacity utilization that is defined as the ratio of actual output to the output that would minimise production costs²². In the *Acclimate* model, the production output that would minimise production costs is given by the baseline production level. Beyond this production level, production costs increase super-linearly. However, for the directly affected regions of NY and NJ, the production capacity is diminished due to the hurricane. We therefore need to adjust the capacity utilization to the applied production capacity reduction. We calculate the change in capacity utilization u for region r at time step t from the applied production shock (i.e., the reduction in production capacity) f , the production level X and the baseline production level X^* as

$$u_r^{(t)} = \frac{X_r^{(t)}}{f_r^{(t)} X_r^*} - 1. \quad (6)$$

Hence, this measure quantifies if and by how much a region is in a state of overproduction, relative to the actual production capacity. In this, we need to adjust the baseline production level X^* with the production capacity reduction factor f_r in case of directly affected regions. A positive value means that the region is in a state of overproduction, causing production costs to increase super-linearly with the production quantity. Negative values indicate proportionality between production quantities and production prices.

Similarly, we define the demand exceedance e for region r at time step t as

$$e_r^{(t)} = \frac{d_r^{(t)}}{f_r^{(t)} X_r^*} - 1, \quad (7)$$

using the incoming demand d that the agent receives. Demand exceedance indicates if fulfilling the entire incoming demand at a given time step would drive the agent into overproduction (for positive values) or not (zero and negative values).

Sectorial and regional aggregation

Sectors in regions are represented by individual agents in the *Acclimate* model. Thus we obtain simulated time series for each sector in every simulated region, individually. A time series of quantity variable q_{ir} of agent ir is classified by its pair of sector i and region r . However, to present comprehensive results, we aggregate time series for variables of interest over sectors or regions. For this we aggregate the quantity variables over the agents ensemble $\{ir\}$:

$$q_{\{ir\}} = \sum_{ir \in \{ir\}} q_{ir} \quad (8)$$

to obtain the sum of quantity values $q_{\{ir\}}$. Quantity variables are, for example, demand quantities or production quantities.

Aggregated price variables $\langle p_{\{ir\}} \rangle$, on the other hand, are calculated as the weighted average over all prices p_{ir} of the individual agents ir :

$$\langle p_{\{ir\}} \rangle = \frac{\sum_{ir \in \{ir\}} p_{ir} q_{ir}}{\sum_{ir \in \{ir\}} q_{ir}}. \quad (9)$$

We note that this aggregation can lead to apparent contradictions when considering, for example, demand exceedance and capacity utilization of aggregated agents. For example, in Fig. 5 the pooled region USA-OTH shows positive demand exceedance and simultaneous low capacity utilization during the first days after the disaster. This is simply a result of the aggregation that we perform over the US regions and their individual sectors. Some agents receive less demand due to the upstream network effect and others experience higher demand to compensate for NY and NJ production outages. While production levels react proportionally to demand changes if the demand exceedance is below zero, they are bound by supply or costs and potential revenue if the demand exceedance is positive. Therefore, the average production for all non-affected US regions is below baseline despite a positive average demand exceedance. However, the longer the scarcity situation prevails, the more agents in the non-affected US receive elevated demand and switch to overproduction, eventually resulting in an increased capacity utilization of USA-OTH as well.

Consumer flexibility to price changes

Consumers with different income tend to have a diverse flexibility if prices change for different commodities and services. This flexibility is integrated into our model by the regionally and sectorally dependent parameter of consumption price elasticity. We divide the regions used in our simulation into four income level groups: low, lower-middle, upper-middle, high income level (Supplementary Tbl. 2). The classification of the income level groups is based on the gross national income (GNI) per capita (GNIpc) of each country. We use the annual, inflation-adjusted definition and classification of income level groups of the World Bank for the year 2012²³. For this calibration, we only focus on average consumer income and do not consider other socio-economic structures (education, regional wealth distribution, etc.).

To obtain empirical parameters, we use the target income elasticities of demand for 140 regions and 10 commodity classes²⁴ of the Global Trade Analysis Project (GTAP)²⁵.

The regional resolutions of EORA and GTAP are not identical. To address this, we set the consumption price elasticities for non-GTAP-countries to the respective income level group parameter. Similarly, the sectoral resolutions of EORA and GTAP are not identical either. To handle this, we map EORA's economic sectors to the GTAP commodity classes and group them into three categories: vital, relevant and other ([Supplementary Tbl. 3](#)). Using these two classification parameters — income level groups of regions and economic relevance categories of sectors — we assign a specific consumption price elasticity from the GTAP data sets²⁶ for any tuple of income level and sector category ([Supplementary Tbl. 4](#)).

With these price elasticities, flexibility to price changes increases with rising income. Therefore, wealthier countries are more resilient against price fluctuations. At the same time, consumers adapt less flexibly to price changes of more life essential goods and services. Since there is little or no substitutability for EORA's large and clearly distinguished sectors ([Supplementary Tbl. 3](#)), we do not consider cross-sector elasticities.

Appendix B: Supplementary figures and tables

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Supplementary Figure 1: Production capacity reduction for Hurricane Sandy. Time-dependent factor with which the production capacity is multiplied, representing the economic shock that results from the hurricane.

Supplementary Figure 2: Consumption change for all simulated regions over their import and export volume with the US. Consumption changes are cumulated for the first 100 days after the hurricane. Size of the scatters indicates the consumption change relative to what regions would consume under baseline conditions during this time. Green and red colors indicate consumption gains and losses, respectively. **a** consumption change over import volume from the US. **b** like panel a for export volume to the US. **c** absolute consumption change over import volume from the US on a log-log scale. Dashed line is the linear fit in the log-log space. **d** like panel c for export volume to the US.

Supplementary Figure 3: Changes of consumption relative to baseline values with recovery time variation. Same as Fig. 3 with longer recovery durations.

Supplementary Figure 4: Changes of consumption relative to baseline values with initial shock intensity variation. Same as Fig. 3 with slightly weaker and stronger initial shock intensity.

Supplementary Figure 5: Global consumption changes after the hurricane with different shock durations. Like Fig. 2 with longer BI recovery times. **left column** Global map. **right column** Detailed zoom on the United States. **a, b** 60 days, **c, d** 80 days, **e, f** 100 days, **g, h** 120 days. Region shapefiles retrieved from GADM²⁷.

Supplementary Table 1: Recovery curve parameters.

State	λ_0	t_r
New York	0.802032	60
New Jersey	0.693088	60

Supplementary Table 2: Regions used in the simulations. Income level corresponds to Gross National Income per capita (GNIpc) of 2012²³.

Income level 1: GNIpc < \$ 1,305

Income level 2: \$ 1,036 < GNIpc < \$ 4,085

Income level 3: \$ 4,086 < GNIpc < \$ 12,615

Income level 4: \$ 12,616 < GNIpc

ISO code	Name	Income level	Geographic region	Consumption change [%]
AFG	Afghanistan	1	Asia	0.004
ALB	Albania	3	Europe	0.010
DZA	Algeria	3	Africa	0.013
AND	Andorra	4	Europe	0.017
AGO	Angola	3	Africa	0.018
ATG	Antigua and Barbuda	4	North America	0.017
ARG	Argentina	3	South America	0.008
ARM	Armenia	2	Asia	0.009
ABW	Aruba	4	South America	0.047
AUS	Australia	4	Oceania	0.008
AUT	Austria	4	Europe	0.014
AZE	Azerbaijan	3	Asia	0.010
BHS	Bahamas	4	North America	0.053
BHR	Bahrain	4	Asia	0.029
BGD	Bangladesh	1	Asia	0.005
BRB	Barbados	4	North America	0.028
BLR	Belarus	3	Europe	0.115
BEL	Belgium	4	Europe	0.015
BLZ	Belize	3	North America	0.016
BEN	Benin	1	Africa	0.004
BMU	Bermuda	4	North America	0.017
BTN	Bhutan	2	Asia	0.008
BOL	Bolivia	2	South America	0.015
BIH	Bosnia and Herzegovina	3	Europe	0.013
BWA	Botswana	3	Africa	0.008
BRA	Brazil	3	South America	0.004
VGB	British Virgin Islands	4	South America	0.026
BRN	Brunei Darussalam	4	Asia	0.029
BGR	Bulgaria	3	Europe	0.017
BFA	Burkina Faso	1	Africa	0.005
BDI	Burundi	1	Africa	0.001
KHM	Cambodia	1	Asia	0.013
CMR	Cameroon	2	Africa	0.006
CAN	Canada	4	North America	-0.053
CPV	Cabo Verde	2	Africa	0.005
CYM	Cayman Islands	4	South America	0.019

ISO code	Name	Income level	Geographic region	Consumption change [%]
CAF	Central African Republic	1	Africa	0.002
TCD	Chad	1	Africa	0.005
CHL	Chile	4	South America	0.010
CN.AH	Anhui	3	China, Asia	0.019
CN.BJ	Beijing	3	China, Asia	0.025
CN.CQ	Chongqing	3	China, Asia	0.021
CN.FJ	Fujian	3	China, Asia	0.024
CN.GS	Gansu	3	China, Asia	0.025
CN.GD	Guangdong	3	China, Asia	0.019
CN.GX	Guangxi	3	China, Asia	0.020
CN.GZ	Guizhou	3	China, Asia	0.024
CN.HA	Hainan	3	China, Asia	0.031
CN.HB	Hebei	3	China, Asia	0.017
CN.HL	Heilongjiang	3	China, Asia	0.019
CN.HE	Henan	3	China, Asia	0.017
CN.HU	Hubei	3	China, Asia	0.018
CN.HN	Hunan	3	China, Asia	0.018
CN.JS	Jiangsu	3	China, Asia	0.020
CN.JX	Jiangxi	3	China, Asia	0.020
CN.JL	Jilin	3	China, Asia	0.020
CN.LN	Liaoning	3	China, Asia	0.023
CN.NM	Nei Mongol	3	China, Asia	0.025
CN.NX	Ningxia Hui	3	China, Asia	0.034
CN.QH	Qinghai	3	China, Asia	0.036
CN.SA	Shaanxi	3	China, Asia	0.020
CN.SD	Shandong	3	China, Asia	0.020
CN.SH	Shanghai	3	China, Asia	0.024
CN.SX	Shanxi	3	China, Asia	0.020
CN.SC	Sichuan	3	China, Asia	0.017
CN.TJ	Tianjin	3	China, Asia	0.027
CN.XJ	Xinjiang Uygur	3	China, Asia	0.023
CN.XZ	Xizang	3	China, Asia	0.046
CN.YN	Yunnan	3	China, Asia	0.021
CN.ZJ	Zhejiang	3	China, Asia	0.021
COL	Colombia	3	South America	0.009
COG	Republic Congo	2	Africa	0.009
CRI	Costa Rica	3	North America	0.022
HRV	Croatia	4	Europe	0.023
CUB	Cuba	3	North America	0.007
CYP	Cyprus	4	Europe	0.026
CZE	Czech Republic	4	Europe	0.024
CIV	Côte d'Ivoire	2	Africa	0.008
PRK	North Korea	1	Asia	0.003
COD	Democratic Republic Congo	1	Africa	0.008

ISO code	Name	Income level	Geographic region	Consumption change [%]
DNK	Denmark	4	Europe	0.014
DJI	Djibouti	2	Africa	0.004
DOM	Dominican Republic	3	North America	0.016
ECU	Ecuador	3	South America	0.016
EGY	Egypt	2	Africa	0.005
SLV	El Salvador	2	North America	0.015
ERI	Eritrea	1	Africa	0.002
EST	Estonia	4	Europe	0.032
ETH	Ethiopia	1	Africa	0.042
FJI	Fiji	3	Oceania	0.025
FIN	Finland	4	Europe	0.018
FRA	France	4	Europe	0.007
PYF	French Polynesia	4	Oceania	0.019
GAB	Gabon	3	Africa	0.017
GMB	Gambia	1	Africa	0.003
GEO	Georgia	2	Asia	0.012
DEU	Germany	4	Europe	0.006
GHA	Ghana	2	Africa	0.012
GRC	Greece	4	Europe	0.015
GRL	Greenland	4	North America	0.014
GTM	Guatemala	2	North America	0.011
GIN	Guinea	1	Africa	0.007
GUY	Guyana	2	South America	0.010
HTI	Haiti	1	North America	0.007
HND	Honduras	2	North America	0.017
HKG	Hong Kong	4	Asia	0.017
HUN	Hungary	3	Europe	0.015
ISL	Iceland	4	Europe	0.039
IND	India	2	Asia	0.005
IDN	Indonesia	2	Asia	0.005
IRN	Iran	3	Asia	0.005
IRQ	Iraq	3	Asia	0.006
IRL	Ireland	4	Europe	0.004
ISR	Israel	4	Asia	0.016
ITA	Italy	4	Europe	0.005
JAM	Jamaica	3	North America	0.022
JPN	Japan	4	Asia	0.004
JOR	Jordan	3	Asia	0.022
KAZ	Kazakhstan	3	Asia	0.006
KEN	Kenya	1	Africa	0.008
KWT	Kuwait	4	Asia	0.021
KGZ	Kyrgyz Republic	1	Asia	0.010
LAO	Lao PDR	2	Asia	0.005
LVA	Latvia	4	Europe	0.029

ISO code	Name	Income level	Geographic region	Consumption change [%]
LBN	Lebanon	3	Asia	0.016
LSO	Lesotho	2	Africa	0.014
LBR	Liberia	1	Africa	0.004
LBY	Libya	3	Africa	0.004
LIE	Liechtenstein	4	Europe	0.000
LTU	Lithuania	4	Europe	0.027
LUX	Luxembourg	4	Europe	0.031
MAC	Macao	4	Asia	0.045
MDG	Madagascar	1	Africa	0.008
MWI	Malawi	1	Africa	0.007
MYS	Malaysia	3	Asia	0.009
MDV	Maldives	3	Asia	0.025
MLI	Mali	1	Africa	0.004
MLT	Malta	4	Europe	0.040
MRT	Mauritania	2	Africa	0.016
MUS	Mauritius	3	Africa	0.018
MEX	Mexico	3	North America	-0.065
MCO	Monaco	4	Europe	0.000
MNG	Mongolia	2	Asia	0.019
MNE	Montenegro	3	Europe	0.003
MAR	Morocco	2	Africa	0.009
MOZ	Mozambique	1	Africa	0.002
MMR	Myanmar	1	Asia	0.001
NAM	Namibia	3	Africa	0.010
NPL	Nepal	1	Asia	0.010
NLD	Netherlands	4	Europe	0.014
ANT	Netherlands Antilles	4	South America	0.044
NCL	New Caledonia	4	Oceania	0.022
NZL	New Zealand	4	Oceania	0.017
NIC	Nicaragua	2	North America	0.015
NER	Niger	1	Africa	0.004
NGA	Nigeria	2	Africa	0.009
NOR	Norway	4	Europe	0.017
PSE	West Bank and Gaza	2	Asia	0.008
OMN	Oman	4	Asia	0.019
PAK	Pakistan	2	Asia	0.005
PAN	Panama	3	South America	0.023
PNG	Papua New Guinea	2	Asia	0.010
PRY	Paraguay	2	South America	0.012
PER	Peru	3	South America	0.012
PHL	Philippines	2	Asia	-0.003
POL	Poland	4	Europe	0.014
PRT	Portugal	4	Europe	0.013
QAT	Qatar	4	Asia	0.011

ISO code	Name	Income level	Geographic region	Consumption change [%]
KOR	South Korea	4	Asia	0.019
MDA	Moldova	2	Europe	0.083
ROU	Romania	3	Europe	0.009
RUS	Russian Federation	4	Asia	0.008
RWA	Rwanda	1	Africa	0.003
WSM	Samoa	2	Oceania	0.005
SMR	San Marino	4	Europe	0.015
STP	São Tomé and Príncipe	2	Africa	0.002
SAU	Saudi Arabia	4	Asia	0.020
SEN	Senegal	2	Africa	0.006
SRB	Serbia	3	Europe	0.007
SYC	Seychelles	3	Africa	0.021
SLE	Sierra Leone	1	Africa	0.005
SGP	Singapore	4	Asia	0.007
SVK	Slovak Republic	4	Europe	0.021
SVN	Slovenia	4	Europe	0.024
SOM	Somalia	1	Africa	0.000
ZAF	South Africa	3	Africa	0.011
SDS	South Sudan	1	Africa	0.000
ESP	Spain	4	Europe	0.007
LKA	Sri Lanka	2	Asia	0.008
SDN	Sudan	2	Africa	0.000
SUR	Suriname	3	South America	0.014
SWZ	Swaziland	2	Africa	0.009
SWE	Sweden	4	Europe	0.013
CHE	Switzerland	4	Europe	0.012
SYR	Syrian Arab Republic	2	Asia	0.007
TWN	Taiwan	4	Asia	0.028
TJK	Tajikistan	1	Asia	0.001
THA	Thailand	3	Asia	0.008
MKD	Macedonia	3	Europe	0.018
TGO	Togo	1	Africa	0.008
TTO	Trinidad and Tobago	4	South America	0.049
TUN	Tunisia	3	Africa	0.011
TUR	Turkey	3	Asia	0.008
TKM	Turkmenistan	3	Asia	0.019
UGA	Uganda	1	Africa	0.005
UKR	Ukraine	2	Europe	0.009
ARE	United Arab Emirates	4	Asia	0.020
GBR	United Kingdom	4	Europe	0.009
TZA	Tanzania	1	Africa	0.014
US.AL	Alabama	4	USA, North America	-0.078
US.AK	Alaska	4	USA, North America	0.017
US.AZ	Arizona	4	USA, North America	-0.106

ISO code	Name	Income level	Geographic region	Consumption change [%]
US.AR	Arkansas	4	USA, North America	-0.028
US.CA	California	4	USA, North America	-0.219
US.CO	Colorado	4	USA, North America	-0.108
US.CT	Connecticut	4	USA, North America	-0.099
US.DE	Delaware	4	USA, North America	0.032
US.DC	District of Columbia	4	USA, North America	-0.031
US.FL	Florida	4	USA, North America	-0.172
US.GA	Georgia	4	USA, North America	-0.139
US.HI	Hawaii	4	USA, North America	-0.007
US.ID	Idaho	4	USA, North America	0.035
US.IL	Illinois	4	USA, North America	-0.166
US.IN	Indiana	4	USA, North America	-0.115
US.IA	Iowa	4	USA, North America	-0.062
US.KS	Kansas	4	USA, North America	-0.054
US.KY	Kentucky	4	USA, North America	-0.074
US.LA	Louisiana	4	USA, North America	-0.097
US.ME	Maine	4	USA, North America	0.047
US.MD	Maryland	4	USA, North America	-0.121
US.MA	Massachusetts	4	USA, North America	-0.139
US.MI	Michigan	4	USA, North America	-0.135
US.MN	Minnesota	4	USA, North America	-0.112
US.MS	Mississippi	4	USA, North America	-0.021
US.MO	Missouri	4	USA, North America	-0.105
US.MT	Montana	4	USA, North America	0.073
US.NE	Nebraska	4	USA, North America	-0.022
US.NV	Nevada	4	USA, North America	-0.045
US.NH	New Hampshire	4	USA, North America	0.021
US.NJ	New Jersey	4	USA, North America	-0.150
US.NM	New Mexico	4	USA, North America	-0.010
US.NY	New York	4	USA, North America	-0.196
US.NC	North Carolina	4	USA, North America	-0.139
US.ND	North Dakota	4	USA, North America	0.050
US.OH	Ohio	4	USA, North America	-0.154
US.OK	Oklahoma	4	USA, North America	-0.071
US.OR	Oregon	4	USA, North America	-0.085
US.PA	Pennsylvania	4	USA, North America	-0.162
US.RI	Rhode Island	4	USA, North America	0.051
US.SC	South Carolina	4	USA, North America	-0.073
US.SD	South Dakota	4	USA, North America	0.073
US.TN	Tennessee	4	USA, North America	-0.108
US.TX	Texas	4	USA, North America	-0.200
US.UT	Utah	4	USA, North America	-0.046
US.VT	Vermont	4	USA, North America	0.120
US.VA	Virginia	4	USA, North America	-0.140

ISO code	Name	Income level	Geographic region	Consumption change [%]
US.WA	Washington	4	USA, North America	-0.133
US.WV	West Virginia	4	USA, North America	0.016
US.WI	Wisconsin	4	USA, North America	-0.107
US.WY	Wyoming	4	USA, North America	0.080
URY	Uruguay	4	South America	0.018
UZB	Uzbekistan	2	Asia	0.003
VUT	Vanuatu	2	Oceania	0.007
VEN	Venezuela	3	South America	0.006
VNM	Vietnam	2	Asia	0.013
YEM	Yemen	2	Asia	0.010
ZMB	Zambia	2	Africa	0.007
ZWE	Zimbabwe	1	Africa	0.026

Supplementary Table 3: Sectors used in the simulations.

Code	Name	Category
AGRI	Agriculture	vital
FISH	Fishing	vital
MINQ	Mining and quarrying	other
GAST	Hotels and restaurants	other
WHOT	Wholesale trade	relevant
OTHE	Others	other
REPA	Maintenance and repair	other
RETT	Retail trade	relevant
FOOD	Food and beverages	vital
TEXL	Textiles and wearing apparel	relevant
TRAN	Transport	relevant
WOOD	Wood and paper	relevant
OILC	Petroleum, chemical & non-metallic mineral products	relevant
FINC	Financial intermediation and business activities	other
METL	Metal products	relevant
MACH	Electrical and machinery	relevant
TREQ	Transport equipment	relevant
MANU	Other manufacturing	relevant
REXI	Re-export and re-import	other
CONS	Construction	relevant
ADMI	Public administration	other
EDHE	Education, health and other services	vital
HOUS	Private households	other
COMM	Post and telecommunications	relevant
RECY	Recycling	other
ELWA	Electricity, gas and water	vital
FCON	Final consumption	relevant

Supplementary Table 4: Consumption price elasticities per income level and sector category. Values are based on GTAP²⁶.

Sector category	Income level			
	1	2	3	4
vital	-0.15	-0.2	-0.3	-0.45
relevant	-0.2	-0.3	-0.4	-0.65
other	-0.3	-0.4	-0.5	-0.75

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